

RESEARCH ARTICLE**Strategic Succession Planning and Continuity of Family Businesses in South East Nigeria****¹Iwuji, Arthur Nnamdi and ²Okechukwu, Elizabeth Uzoamaka PhD**^{1,2}*Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT)****Corresponding Author: Iwuji, Arthur Nnamdi | Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT)****ABSTRACT**

The study examined the Effect of Strategic Succession Planning and continuity of Family Business in South East Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to: ascertain the effect of leadership on the growth of family businesses and the extended family members' commitment affect continuity in a family-owned business in South East Nigeria. A descriptive survey was adopted. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16.0 were used. To confirm the significance of the correlation between variables, Pearson correlation analysis was performed. The study revealed that leadership has a significant effect on the growth of family businesses in southeast Nigeria. This was true with $t = 13.601$; $M = 2.78$; $Std = 0.059$; $p < .05$; It was indicated that family members' commitment can significantly affect the continuity of family business in southeast Nigeria with $t = 18.20$; $M = 2.79$; $Std = 0.043$; $p < .05$. The study concluded that lack of management of succession planning can pose great challenges in the continuity of family businesses. The family must explore its values, family business philosophy, and family vision to assess its commitment to the business for developing family members for management and leadership roles.

Keywords: *Strategic Succession Planning; Continuity of Family Businesses; South East Nigeria*

Introduction

A family business may be defined as any business in which two or more family members are involved and the majority of ownership or control lies within a family (*Randel, Kets-de-Vries, and Florent-Treacy, 2019*). In some countries, many of the largest publicly listed firms are family-owned. A firm is said to be family-owned if a person is a controlling shareholder; that is, a person (rather than a state, corporation, management trust, or mutual fund) can garner enough shares to assure at least 20% of the voting rights and the highest percentage of voting rights in comparison to other shareholders (*Chakrabarty, 2009*). In a family business, two or more members of the management team are drawn from the owning family. Family businesses may also be managed by individuals who are not members of the family (*Alderson, 2011*). However, a broad general definition of a family firm is one where a family owns enough of the equity to be able to exert control over strategy and is involved in top management

positions. In Nigeria, many businesses that are now public companies were once family businesses. The founder of a business is a major source of knowledge and expertise and the owner's social networks represent important intangible assets for the company.

Family business succession is the process of transitioning the management and the ownership of the business to the next generation of family members (*Walsh, 2016*). However, a broad general definition of a family firm is one where a family owns enough of the equity to be able to exert control over strategy *and* is involved in top management positions (*Walsh, 2016*). *Rodrigo (2013)* defines succession planning as the process of identifying and preparing suitable employees through mentoring, training, and job rotation, to replace key players within an organization as those key players leave their positions for whatever reasons such as retirement, advancement, and attrition. The Family-Owned Businesses (FOB) in Nigeria are mostly small and Medium Enterprises (SMES) (*Obadan and Ohiorenoya, 2013; Onuoha, 2015*). They create employment opportunities, have and capacity to reduce poverty, inequality, and social vices, are catalysts of innovation, inventions, and creativity; stimulate indigenous entrepreneurship; link up the various sectors and sub-sectors of the economy; pay taxes which enable governments to provide basic amenities; and contribute to regional activities and cooperation (*Onuoha, 2013*).

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The future prosperity of both family and business depends upon how well understanding and contacts are passed on and how far these are trusted and valued by the next generation (Lee, Lim and Lim, 2013). Successfully transferring family businesses to the next generation raises complex and emotional problems. Planning for the transition cannot start too early, and the whole process needs to be very carefully managed. But many entrepreneurs are reluctant to face up to the thought of giving up control, and succession is one of the main causes of divisions and tensions that can damage family life and undermine business performance. The most significant challenge faced by family businesses is a survival from one generation to the next. Optimizing the likelihood of business survival requires family businesses to lay forth a workable plan for securing next-generation involvement. Continuity of these core business values is essential for upholding a long-standing business image that both external and internal stakeholders will recognize. Management and ownership succession are two critical factors around which all other business activities revolve (Onuoha, 2013)

Statement of the Problem

Family businesses make a big cumulative contribution to jobs and exports. A lot of big companies these days are eager to copy the speed of decisions and the entrepreneurial flair that family business ownership and control are thought to confer. However, family businesses nowadays face the frightening challenge of changing leaders at a time of rapid technological change and increased competitive forces from globalization. Most family businesses appear to struggle with leadership succession between different generations of family members. The challenge for any business is continuity as one generation plans for retirement or it may come as a surprise resignation from a key employee or an employee is lost due to death or long-term disability.

The biggest problem with the family-owned business may be attributed to a lack of strategic succession planning. Indeed, poorly planned successions are among the biggest value-destroying events for family businesses. Families hesitate to plan succession because they are uncertain how the interests, choices, and decisions of different family members will play out over the years or decades. Growth also may be a dilemma if some relatives are reluctant to plough profits back into the business. Without the family's commitment, there can be no parallel planning process. If the family cannot develop a shared commitment to invest and participate in the business, then it may be time to sell or liquidate. Despite these challenges, it is pertinent to examine the effects of strategic succession planning on the continuity of family businesses in southeaster states of Nigeria, and finding a solution to it would be rewarding.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine strategic succession planning and continuity of Family Businesses (FB) in South East Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study were:

- I. To ascertain the effect of leadership on the growth of family businesses in South East Nigeria.
- II. To ascertain the extent family members commitment, affect survival of family-owned business in South East Nigeria.

Statement of Hypotheses

- I. Leadership has no positive significant effect on the growth of family businesses in South East Nigeria.
- II. family members commitment to an extent have no positive significant effect on the survival of family business in South East Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Family Businesses

A family business is a commercial organization in which family exercises control over business in the form of ownership or in the form of management of the firm where family members are employed on key positions Ghadoliya (2020). They are closely identified with the firm through leadership or ownership. In a family business, two or more members within the management team are drawn from the owning family. Family businesses may also be managed by individuals who are not members of the family. However, family members are often involved

in the operations of their family business in some capacity and, in smaller companies, usually one or more family members are the senior officers and managers (*Randel, et al, 2016*).

Succession Planning

Succession planning involves the identification and development of potential successors in an organization. It is referring to as the process of pinpointing key needs for leadership and intellectual talent throughout the organization over time and preparing individuals for present and future work responsibilities. In a family business succession planning involves: strategic planning, financial planning, estate planning, and human resources planning. This planning prepares for future critical vacancies of management positions by forecasting the talent necessary for these roles to provide the groundwork and understanding of the characteristics needed to maintain a company's strategic plan.

Strategic Succession Business Planning

Poutziouris (2010) defines strategic planning as the processes used to plan for the long-term performance of an organization. It creates insights into the company and its environment. Strategic successive planning centering on both business and family goals is vital to successful family businesses. In fact, planning may be more crucial to family businesses than to other types of business entities, because in many cases families have a majority of their assets tied up in the business. Since much conflict arises due to a disparity between family and business goals, planning is required to align these goals and formulate a strategy for reaching them. The ideal plan will allow the company to balance family and business needs to everyone's advantage.

Leadership

Western (2013) opines *that* Leadership is a practical skill, encompasses the ability of an individual, group or organization to "lead", influence or guide other individuals, members, teams, or entire organizations. Although continuity of leadership is a key strength in businesses. The long physical presence of a founder in a business, whether running the business directly or not, enables the articulation and dissemination of a consistent vision and strategy for the business. One remarkable aspect of successful family business continuity is a founder's ability to embed strong core values and a clear vision, while also developing the managerial skills of key leaders, something not all founders are able to do. The viability of any business succession is inextricably linked to the organization's preparedness in thoughtfully addressing leadership transition and sustainability long before the business is faced with this reality. Collins (2011) outlines the characteristic of a great leader is one who sets up the company to succeed after the founder is gone.

Family Commitment

Commitment to work is defined as the level of enthusiasm an individual has towards his/her tasks assigned at a workplace. It is the feeling of responsibility that an individual has towards the goals, mission, and vision of the organization he/she is working with. The family's commitment is the foundation for creating unity of purpose and maintaining family harmony. The format, or even the content, of these actions is not as important as the process for developing them. Family Commitment is a priority discussion for the family because it supports the development of the shared future vision and the family enterprise continuity plan. Simply, a family that plans its future together can build stronger family relationships and new opportunities for family participation and achievement (Dauda, 2013).

Business Growth

Business growth is a incident that occurs when business owners, employees and outside factors influence the success of a company. Growing a business takes planning and concentrated efforts. Growth means increasing sales, assets, net profits and a chance to take advantage of the experience curve to reduce the per unit cost of products sold and thereby increasing profits (Sumari; 2013). A business grows when it expands a customer base, increases revenue or produces more products. Growth is the goal of most businesses and is the reason behind many decisions that affect the daily workings of a company both internally and externally. Business growth is impacted by consumer trends, market opportunities and decisions made by company leadership.

Business Survival

Business survival refers to keeping the **business** operating for a certain amount of time, especially when some crisis situation comes. Survival may be an important objective, if a business is being threatened by a takeover from a larger more established business. The main objective for the management of the enterprise will be to persuade the owners (shareholders) not to sell their shares to the person or company bidding for them. When trading of goods and services becomes difficult because of recession or lack of the market, individual businesses or industries will face difficulties, or even get out of business. So, survival during difficult times becomes a main objective.

Theoretical Framework

Relay Succession Planning Model

Santorin (2004) came up with the “Relay Succession Planning” This model says that the responsibility of the designation that is about to be vacant should be passed to the successor over a long period of time. The successor will be exposed to the corporate challenges in the pre-succession phase under the guidance of the person who is designated at the soon to be vacant position and hence he/she is tested at the period of his/her training under the predecessor. Relay Succession Planning Model allows the organization to have time for selection, training, assessment, grooming of the successor and hence helps in creating a transition timetable because an heir who is apparent is selected a few years before the person at the key position is about to retire. The successor then works with the soon to be predecessor. And therefore, the successor performs better because he/she is already tried in decisiveness and crisis management.

Empirical Review

Westhuizen, & Andrea (2014) investigated correlation between leadership practices and business performance amongst first- and second-generation owners of family firms in South Africa. A self-administered, quantitative survey questionnaire, measuring leadership practices and business performance was distributed via means of a non-probability, snowball sampling method to 197 first- and second-generation family business owners in the Sedibeng region of South Africa. The findings indicate that positive significant correlations exist between the occurrence of leadership practices and business performance for first generation leaders of the selected family businesses, but limited correlations exist between the variables for the second-generation leaders.

Maguta (2016) examined the effects of succession planning practices on the performance of (NGOs) in Kenya. The study engaged both qualitative and quantitative data obtained from 15 NGOs, then presented the analyzed data through illustrative frequency distributions. The descriptive and content analysis was used for analysis. Pearson correlation coefficient were used to analyze the variables in the study. The study identified succession planning as persistent concern for (NGOs) pursuing performance sustainability.

Onyeukwu & Jekelle (2019) investigated leadership succession and sustainability of small family-owned businesses in Anambra, South East Nigeria. The study employed the survey research design. The study employed Pearson Product Moment Correlation to determine the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The findings revealed that, mentoring and human capital development has significant influence on sustainability of small family-owned businesses.

Sami & Paul-Laurent (2019) investigated family member’s commitment to the firm and family business continuity: investigating the mediating role of family-to-firm identity fit and emotional attachment. The study offers an explanatory model of family business continuity intentions where it is hypothesized that high family influence on the firm implies a high commitment of family members to the firm and thus a high desire to sustain the family firm in the long run. In addition, the model emphasizes the mediating role of family members' identification with the firm as well as their emotional attachment in explaining the influence of family members' commitment on continuity intentions. The findings show that family member’s commitment to the firm is positively related to the owning family's influence on the firm.

Jose (2007) investigated succession in family business in Canada. The study focused on succession process in Molson family business. They adopted a longitudinal approach to identify and evaluated the crucial activities and processes that have assisted facilitated succession in the Molson family business. The study argued that it is only when succession plan is effective, that is only when conflict could be avoided in among the family members engaged in succession.

Esuh, Mohd, and Adebayo (2011) explored and examined succession in relation to family business continuity in Nigeria and thus, offered a conceptual framework on succession in relation to family business continuity. Factor analysis, correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis were the data analysis techniques. The study proposed founder, successor and environment will jointly affect family business continuity and that true succession will mediate the relationship between founder, successor and environment, and family business continuity.

Zahrani¹, Nikmaram and Latifi (2014) conducted a study to investigate the impact of family business characteristics on successor planning process in such businesses in Tehran industrial towns in Iran. Statistical population of this research consists of managers or supervisors from 68,000 industrial units in Tehran. Industrial Towns are selected and sample population is identified as 120 samples. Spearman's correlation test and SPSS 16 were used to test the hypotheses. The findings indicated that there is a positive and significant relationship between business family characteristics especially the tendency of trusted people to succeeding and successor planning.

Salama (2014) conducted an empirical study on the relationship between succession planning practices and employee retention in large media houses in Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Data was then analyzed using descriptive statistics and analysis of variances. From the study, the findings reveal that there is a positive relationship between succession planning practices and employee retention. The findings also suggest that career management is critical as majority of the employees feel that there are no clear career paths and if they exist, they are too narrow.

Maguta (2016) examined the effects of succession planning practices on the performance of (NGOs) in Kenya. The study engaged both qualitative and quantitative data obtained from 15 NGOs, then presented the analyzed data through illustrative frequency distributions. The descriptive and content analysis was used for analysis. It indicated that succession planning entailing staff retention, addressing organizational conflicts, and meeting shareholder expectations showed a positive association with the performance of NGOs. Conclusively, the study identified succession planning as the persistent concern for (NGOs) pursuing performance sustainability. There was an existing gap between conventional management of (NGOs) in Nairobi and the adoption of succession planning practices.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was utilized for the study. Descriptive research is concerned with the description of data and characteristics about a population. The study adopts primary source of data. Structured questionnaire was the source of the primary data. The researcher got this information from the respondents. The study was conducted in south east Nigeria with reference to some selected medium and large-scale enterprises that registered with their State Ministry of Commerce, Industry and Tourism. The population of the study consisted of selected medium and large-scale enterprises located in south east Nigeria that are family-owned business. One is selected from each state but Ebonyi state has none. The total population of the study is five thousand, two hundred and forty-six (5,246). The instrument for data collection utilized for the study was structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was structured in line with the variables of the study already stated in the hypotheses. The Likert-type scale or category was adopted for analysis, namely: strongly agree; (SA); Agree (A); Undecided (UD); Disagree (DA); and Strongly Disagree (SD). Each level is assigned a number ranging from 5 (SA) to 1 (SD). Also used were Very Great Extent (VGE), Great Extent (GE), Some Extent (SE), Little Extent (LE), and Very Little Extent (VLE). Each level was assigned a number ranging from 5 (VGE) to 1 (VLE). Qualitative data was analyzed descriptively. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) versions 16.0 were used. The data collected with regards to each of the questions were also analyzed using in tables, frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation and ANOVA.

Freund and Williams (1986) statistical sampling formula were applied to obtain the sample size from the population. The formula is given as thus:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 N p q}{N e^2 + Z^2 p q}$$

Where,

Z = Probability given under 95% reliability

N = Population of the study

- e = Sampling error
- p = proportion of success
- q = proportion of failure
- n = sample size sought

Substituting the value into the formula, we have:

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 (5246) (0.5) (0.5)}{5246 (0.05)^2 + (1.96)^2 (0.5) (0.05)}$$

$$n = \frac{(3.8416) (5246) (0.25)}{5246 (0.0025) + 3.8416 (0.25)}$$

$$n = \frac{5038}{13.115 + 0.9604}$$

$$n = \frac{5038}{14.0754}$$

$$n = 357.9$$

$$n = 358$$

Therefore, a total number of three hundred and fifty-eight respondents were used for the study.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The data collected with regards to each of the questions were analyzed using in tables, frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation and ANOVA

Distribution and Return of Questionnaire

Table 1: Distribution and Return Rate of Respondents

<i>Industries</i>	<i>Copies of questionnaire sent out</i>	<i>Copies of questionnaire returned</i>	<i>Copies of questionnaire not returned</i>	<i>Percentage of returned and verified copies</i>
<i>RokanaInd.Ltd.</i>	90	72	18	20
<i>CutixPlc</i>	103	75	28	21
<i>Juhel Nigeria Ltd</i>	86	61	25	17
<i>Mikko Plastics</i>	79	55	24	15
<i>Total</i>	358	263	95	73

Source: Field Survey, 2022

From Table 1, it was shown that out of the total number three hundred fifty-eight (358) questionnaire administered, two hundred and sixty-three (263) of them were returned giving a percentage of 73% while ninety-five (95) of them were not returned giving a percentage of 27%.

Data Relating to Research Questions

Table 2: Leadership has significant effect on the growth of Family Business

<i>Responses</i>	<i>Rokana</i>	<i>Cutix</i>	<i>Juhel</i>	<i>Mikko</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>Strongly agree</i>	43	50	41	42	176	67
<i>Agree</i>	5	8	5	5	23	44
<i>Undecided</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Strongly disagree</i>	16	10	12	8	46	17
<i>Disagree</i>	8	7	3	0	18	7
<i>Total</i>	72	75	61	55	263	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 2 showed the responses on whether leadership has significant effect on the growth of family business. 176 respondents (67%) out of 263 respondents strongly agreed that leadership tussle has significant effect on the growth of family business, 23 (9%) respondents agreed, 46 (17%) respondents strongly disagreed, while 18 (7%) respondents disagreed.

Table 3: Effect of Family Members’ Commitment on the continuity of family-owned business in south eastern states of Nigeria.

Options	SA (5)	A (4)	UD (3)	SD (2)	D (1)	N	\bar{X}	Remark
<i>Plays a pivotal role in its short and long-term success</i>	162	85	2	5	9	263	4.47	Accepted
<i>Helps effectively manage their family component</i>	99	70	4	56	34	263	4	Accepted
<i>Integrate family members into the management and ownership succession processes</i>	118	88	5	35	17	263	4	Accepted
<i>Establishing family Communication</i>	151	61	4	37	10	263	4	Accepted
<i>Serve to guide the overall succession process</i>	87	100	0	25	51	263	4	Accepted
<i>Lacks initiative</i>	45	18	0	92	108	263	2.2	Rejected

Source: Field Survey 2022

In the table 3 mean responses from 3.00 and above were accepted as effect of family members’ commitment on the strategic succession planning of family business, while mean response below 3.00 were rejected.

Table 4: Spearman’s Correlation Coefficients among Research Variables

	Succession Planning	Survival of the Business	Commitment	Leadership
<i>Succession planning</i>	1			
<i>growth</i>	0.066	1		
<i>Commitment</i>	0.433	0.161	1	
<i>Leadership</i>	0.626	0.286	0.400	1

All coefficients are significant in 95% confidence level.

Spearman’s correlation coefficient was 0.512 between family business variables and succession planning and this rate was significant in 99% confidence level. Table 4 outlines the results of Spearman’s correlation test between succession planning and family business aspects. Coefficient of correlation propensity of leadership successor to take over has the most amount among all coefficients (0.626**) and is higher than the average. On the other hand, coefficient of correlation of survival of the business the family business has the least amount (0.066**). In general, this study shows that all relationships between variables are positive and significant and approximately coefficients of correlation of all variables are average and more than it. As seen, there is a significant correlation among all variables.

Table 5: Model Description

Model	Correlation Coefficient	Squared Correlation Coefficient	Moderated Correlation Coefficient
1	0.670	0.499	0.37858

In table 5, regression test was applied to study the casual relations between family business variables and succession planning. In Table 5, squared correlation coefficient is 0.499 which means that 49.9% of changes in succession planning can be explained by family business variables.

Table 6: Regression Model Summary of Strategic Succession Planning of Family Businesses

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.8566	0.7338	0.7011	0.7638

Predictors: (Constant), family business survival, commitment, changes in leadership and continuity of the business

To test for the combined influence of succession strategy variables on family businesses, the relevant outputs of the multiple regression analysis were used. From the results shown in table 6, the model shows a goodness of fit as indicated by the coefficient of determination (R²) with a value of 0.7338. This implies that the independent variable, strategic succession planning explains 73.38 percent of the variations of continuity and growth of family businesses. The study therefore identifies strategic succession planning as a critical factor affecting family businesses.

Table 7: ANOVA Table

Mean	Squares total	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	13.553	3	4.518	31.520	0.000
Remained	16.626	116	0.143		
Total	30.180	119			

ANOVA Table was used to study the certainty of the relationship between family business variables and succession planning. As seen, sig rate is less than 0.05 which shows that regression model has been able to explain changes in the dependent variable (succession planning).

Table 8: Analysis of Succession Planning and Survival of Family Business

	Succession Planning	Survival of family business
Succession Planning Pearson Correlation	1	.837**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
N	263	263
Survival of family business Pearson Correlation	.837**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
1	263	310

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Based on the confirmation of directionality shown in Table 8, sufficient evidence exists to accept hypothesis H₄ that there is positive relationship between succession planning and survival of family business in south eastern states of Nigeria at a confidence level of 0.95.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 9: Analysis of t-Test Statistics Variables effect on Strategic Succession Planning and Family Businesses

Variables	t	Df	Sig	Mean Diff.	Std error
Survival	1.111	214	.200	1.60	.064
Commitment	18.20	214	.040	2.79	.043
Leadership	13.601	214	.070	2.78	.059

Source: Field survey, 2022

Table 9 is a summary of the t-test value on the mean and level of significance of the items tested. The result of the test shows that the t-calculated value was only significant for all the items at 5%. Therefore, the variables in the hypotheses affirm that strategic succession planning has positive and significant on family businesses in south eastern states of Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Leadership has Positive Significant Effect on the growth of Family-Owned Business in South Eastern States in Nigeria

In table 9 Ratios and significance of variables are outlined. According to figures in Beta column, one can say that among the mentioned variables, the propensity of leadership to take over has the highest impact on successor planning. Collins (1991) agrees that a great leader is one who sets up the company to succeed after the founder is gone.

Family Members' Commitment have Significantly Positive Effect Survival of Family Businesses in South East Nigeria.

Spearman's correlation coefficient was 0.512 between family business variables and succession planning and this rate was significant in 99% confidence level. Table 8 outlines the results of Spearman's correlation test between succession planning and family business aspects. In general, this study shows that all relationships between variables are positive and significant and approximately coefficients of correlation of all variables are average and more than it. As seen, there is a significant correlation among all variables. Walsh (2011) asserts that many multigenerational family businesses have successfully managed their family component during the succession process.

Summary of Findings

- I. The study revealed that leadership has significant effect on the growth of family businesses in south east Nigeria. This was true with $t = 13.601$; $M = 2.78$; $Std = 0.059$; $p < .05$.
- II. It was indicated that family members commitment can significantly affect continuity of family business in south eastern states in Nigeria with $t = 18.20$; $M = 2.79$; $Std = 0.043$; $p < .05$.

Conclusion

The study concluded that poor or lack of management of succession planning can pose great challenges in the continuity of family businesses. A family business owned and managed by a family will produce lifetime work relationships. For this reason, family must explore its values, family business philosophy and family vision to assess its commitment to the business for developing family members for management and leadership roles.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and results of this study the following recommendations were made.

- I. Preparing a Succession Plan, including arranging for successor training and setting a retirement date. They should create an environment that supports participation.
- II. Family enterprise continuity plan should be developed that complement the Business Strategy Plan. The family must explore its values, family business philosophy and family vision to assess its commitment to the business for developing family members for management and leadership roles.

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